

CAA Netherland-Flanders National Chapter Information and Report

National Chapter*: Netherland-Flanders

Submitted by*: Ronald Visser, Devi Taelman, Alex Brandsen and Alicia Walsh

Date Submitted*: 1 February 2026

Chapter Organisational Details

Chapter Leadership

Term Dates for the Current Steering Committee:

Name*	Chapter Position*	Email Address
Ronald Visser	Chair	r.m.visser@saxion.nl
Devi Taelman	Treasurer	devi.taelman@vub.be
Alex Brandsen	Communications officer	a.brandsen@arch.leidenuniv.nl
Alicia Walsh	Secretary	a.s.c.walsh@arch.leidenuniv.nl

CAA Steering Committee Representative*: Ronald Visser

This is often the chair, but any member of the chapter's leadership can be designated as the Steering Committee representative. However, the Steering Committee representative **must be a member of CAA International** while serving in this capacity.

Chapter Membership

Total Number of Current Members: 183

If you have different categories membership categories for Full Members, Students, and/or Low Income Members, please provide the numbers of members at each level:

Membership Level	Number of Members
No levels, because membership is free	191

Chapter Contact Information

Chapter Website*: <https://caanfl.nl/>

Chapter Social Media Channel(s) (optional):

Platform*	Handle*
Twitter (X)	https://twitter.com/caanfl (not in use)
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/caanfl/
Instagram	-
LinkedIn	-
YouTube	-
Mastodon	https://akademienl.social/@caanfl

General Contact Email for the Chapter*:

info@caanfl.nl

Chapter Description

Brief Description of Your Chapter*:

CAA Netherlands – Flanders (CAA-NL-FL) represents the Dutch and Flemish national chapter of the international CAA. Its main aim is to bring together archaeologists, mathematicians and computer scientists based in the Netherlands and Flanders, thus encouraging communication between these disciplines and giving an overview of current work in the field. Through yearly meetings, CAA-NL-FL wishes to stimulate discussion and future progress.

CAA-NL was founded on 26 September 1996 and became CAA-NL-FL in 2010 as a joint chapter for the Netherlands and Flanders, because we share the same language. It has been a growing community ever since. We organise an annual Chapter Meeting, and every two years this takes the form of a joint event with our German colleagues (CAA-DE). Our goal is to provide a platform that welcomes both established and early career researchers to present their work and engage in dialogue.

The organisation is currently administered by four speakers: Ronald Visser, Alicia Walsh, Devi Taelman, and Alex Brandsen. Membership of CAA-NL-FL is free and open to all. Anyone attending a meeting of CAA-NL-FL automatically becomes a member.

Report for the CAA National Chapter of Netherlands-Flanders

Reporting Period*: 2025

Netherlands-Flanders

Submitted by*: Ronald Visser, Devi Taelman, Alex Brandsen and Alicia Walsh

Date Submitted*: 2-2-2026

Update on the National Chapter Activities:*

In 2025, a large number of our members participated in the international CAA conference in Athens. They contributed actively by organising several sessions (e.g. S05, S06, S10, S12, S22, S23 and S43) and by presenting papers both within these sessions and across many others. This strong presence reflects the active and ongoing involvement of our chapter in the international CAA community.

In 2025, we organised our Local Chapter Meeting in Flanders, which brought together approximately 50 participants. The event took place in Brussels on December 9 and 10 and was hosted AMGC research group at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB). The topics of the lectures were highly diverse, reflecting the breadth of research interests and the variety of backgrounds within our Chapter. The presentations resulted in interesting and productive discussions. We also welcomed several new members into our community, and laid the foundations for new collaborations and friendships. Overall, the two-day meeting was a success.

The full programme can be found below. Abstracts for the papers can be found in the last section on the website (<https://nlfl.caa-international.org/events/meetings/local-chapter-meeting-2025/>).

Day 1 – Tuesday, 9 December 2025

12:30 – 12:50 Registration

12:50 – 13:00 Welcome, introduction and practicalities

Session 1 – Data Analysis & Quantitative Methods

13:00 – 13:25 Dries Daems: Pottery Networks in Late Hellenistic and Early Roman Anatolia and Levant

13:25 – 13:50 Laura Van der Knaap: Connecting demographic agent-based models to skeletal data: the case of the Roman cemetery at Tiel-Passewaaij

13:50 – 14:15 Marta Galindo Diaz: Ancient Cities, Modern Tools: Quantifying the Environmental Impact of the Roman Bath-Gymnasium at Sagalassos through LCA

14:15 – 14:40 Hannah James: From Baselines to Origins: Quantitative approaches to reconstructing human and animal mobility using strontium isotopes

Session 2 – Data Management & Data Architecture (Parts I & II combined)

14:40 – 15:05 Wouter Yperman: The 25 year road towards digital field recording

15:05 – 15:20 Coffee break

15:20 – 15:45 Matthias Lang: From PDF to DataFrame: A Pragmatic Workflow for Extracting Roman-Era Archaeological Data from Legacy Reports

15:45 – 16:10 Florian Thiery: Bridging Stones and Volcanoes: Can Semantic Modelling, Visualisation, and Little Minions Bridge Archaeology and Geosciences?

16:10 – 16:35 Ben Bellefroid: Echoes from the Past: a Citizen Science Platform for Archaeological LiDAR Prospection

16:35 – 17:00 Phaedra Criaco: Managing Legacy Data in Archaeological Science: A Cautionary Tale

Social drink / reception + Dinner (optional and at your own expense)

Wednesday, 10 December 2025

09:00 – 09:30 Registration

Session 3 – GIS Applications / Remote Sensing & Landscape Archaeology

09:30 – 09:55 Dries Vergouwen: Visualizing River Histories: A Digital Approach to the Senne Valley in Brussels

09:55 – 10:20 Emma Legrand: Understanding human mobility in northern Croatia: Combining strontium isotope analyses and GIS applications

10:20 – 10:45 Simon Jaxy: Semi-Supervised Modeling of Archaeological Potential in the Late Antique Sagalassos Area

10:45 – 11:00 Coffee break

11:00 – 11:25 Andrei Kedich: Detection of anthropogenic closed depressions in the Belgian Loess Belt and their relationship to archaeological evidence

Session 4 – Theoretical, Conceptual & Critical Approaches

11:50 – 13:00 Lunch break

13:00 – 13:25 Alicia Walsh: The Ethical Divide: Critical assessments of digital recording methods in Dutch archaeological practice

13:25 – 13:50 Foteini Tsigoni: Negotiation of Cultural Authority: 3D reconstruction of the Frankish Propylaea

Session 5 – Digital Documentation Techniques

13:50 – 14:15 Rosie Campbell : Reconstructing Dhaskalio: Integrating Legacy with Born-Digital Data

14:15 – 14:40 Polte De Weirdt: Old Data, New Horizons: 3D Modeling as a Catalyst for Recontextualizing Fragmentary Legacy Data

14:40 – 15:05 Tuba Unal: Virtual reconstruction as a tool for presenting historical evolution of archaeological sites: Nysa ad Maeandrum

15:05 – 15:30 CAA-NL-FL Annual General Meeting, conclusions and goodbye